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Language Technologies in
Humanities:
Computational Semantic
Analysis in Folkloristics

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Folk Song Lyrics

- Can we analyze **lyrics** and infer
 - song type (e.g. love, moral, legendary, drinking ...)
 - relations between songs
- Melodies in oral traditions are often borrowed, transferred between songs

love?
moral?
legendary?
death?
drinking?
family?

Corpus

- Newly created from books *Slovenske ljudske pesmi I-V* ZRC SAZU (1970-2007)
 - scan/OCR
- 4095 Slovenian folk **narrative** poems
 - from 18th century on
 - 349 variants
 - from 1 to 180 songs per variant

V

Conversion

- Separate lyrics, metadata

mikrofon vključen. Sprva raztrgana, skromna obnova je mimogrede prerasla v samostojno verzijo naše pesmi — B. V nji najdemo nekaj novih prvin, ki jih tu natisnjena verzija (A) nima:

Matjaža so dali v ječo. Linčica se je vanj zaljubila, menda je bil lep človek. Linčica je dala »dór-mido« (uspavalni napoj ali prašek) očetu in materi, kasneje pa je uspavala tudi stražo. O mostu, ki je slonel na lažnih opornikih in ki sta ga ubežnika

zadnji hip pred prihodom zasledovavcev zažgala, slišimo, da je bil na meji (turške dežele).

Za pesem, ki je na sarnem začetku okrnjena, pomenijo ti dodatki dragoceno dopolnilo. Ob nadržnosti, da je Linčica dala očetu in materi napoj za spanje (dopolnilo pevkine sestre Marije), se je Ana celo glasno začudila, kot bi hotela reči: »Glej glej, tega pa nisem vedela!« ali »Na to pa sem pozabila!«

6.

Kraj: Bila v Reziji

Pela in pripovedovala: Ana Buttolo, vd. Zanetti, Pécawa (1894)

B

Z p.s.: Matičetov-Vodušek, 20. junija 1963

$\text{♩} = 122 - 136$ Poco rubato

1. Lin-či-ca tur-kin-če-ca, na wze-la no-ga Won-gar-ja.
3. — Kar je bil pro-žo-nir, (i.d.)

¹ Od 4. kitice dalje na tem mestu »«.

- | | |
|--|--|
| 1. Linčica Turkinčica
na wzela noga Wóngarja. | 9. Dwa dni na jě mu púlela
nú na jě mu fys raklá: |
| 2. To bila noga kraja šči
nu won to bil de Wóngar krei, | 10. »Da ti me vliku fes plažáš
nu ti maš víde' me womožé» |
| 3. ke an je bil prožonir
nu za tri dni je bil zažán. | 11. ke ja éon te wiğá' wozdē,
ja bon te fis wiğál' wozdē.« |
| 4. Nu Linčici je zaplažél,
na je prosila grač(jico). ¹ | 12. »Káko béj maš mé wóženē,
ke já si wžž wóženjen, |
| 5. Nu won je jo koncédinal,
na drě delá pokléknula | 13. a) ma já man žée dwa bratra tapar
iši,
b) man dwa lipča bratra někoj mle, ²
ke tédwa tó bo te wzéto.« |
| 6. nu nōge na mu búšnula
nu drě ga búšnula pa njağá. | |
| 7. »Da Linčeca Turkinčeca,
wse tō ke boš me bārala, | |
| 8. já ja bon te kontantəl,
ke ti si moja sama ščíl» | Nu dwa dni na je mu púliła jěst
anu kjüče na je ískala
wod te wílikih dur tow Fránčiji,
ke grejo skuz,
na wlika galerija skuz, |

6. B ¹ Linčica Turkinčica / je vzela Ogra, / ² je bila kraljeva hči / in on je bil kralj Oger, / (5) ³ ki je bil jetnik, / in za tri dni je bil zaprt / ⁴ in Linčica se je zaljubila vanj, / Ona je prosila [očeta] dobroto / [da bi nosila 3 dni jetniku jest v ječo]. / ⁵ In on je privolil. / (10) Ona je dol pokleknila / ⁶ in noge mu poljubila / in brč poljubila še njega. / ⁷ »Oj Linčica Turkinčica, / vse, kar me boš prosila, / (15) ⁸ jaz te bom zadovoljil, / ker ti si moja edina hči!« / ⁹ Dwa dni mu [jetniku] je nosila [jest] / in ona mu je rekla: / ¹⁰ »Ti si mi prav močno všeč / (20) in ti glej, da se oženiš z mano, / ¹¹ ker jaz te bom rešila od tod, / jaz te bom resnično rešila od tod!« / ¹² »Káko se boš omožila z mano, / saj jaz sem že oženjen! / (25) ¹³ a) Ampak jaz imam še dva brata doma, / lepša od mene.« / b) Imam dva lepša brata kot sem jaz, / ta dva te bosta vzela!« / In dva dni mu je nosila jest, / in ključje je iskala / (30) od velikih duri v Franciji, / ki gredo skozi, / skozi velik

Conversion

1. Replacement **Rules**
symbols characteristic of dialect groups (semivowels, diphthongization, pitch accent etc.) are replaced by their grammatical equivalents
2. A **dialect dictionary** is used to translate the words into literary language
>18000 words/forms
3. Morphosyntactic tagger for the Slovenian language **Obeliks** was used for lemmatization
 - tags the words with morphological features
 - provides **lemmas**

A Nəč predowga, nəč prekratka,
sej ne bom plesala_u nji.

...
bešta tecita
bət biti
beteg bolečin
...

C nič predolg nič prekratek
saj ne biti plesati v on

Experiments

- Narrow context, just 2 song **families:**
 - love and fate conflicts
 - family fates and conflicts
- **Themes** related to death, murder, suicide, infidelity, punishment, e.g.
 - Death of a bride before wedding
 - Nun's suicide for love
 - Unfaithful student
 - Poisoning of own sister
 - ...
- Strong **intertextuality**
 - traveling of verses, motifs, and thematic patterns from one song to the other

Experiment one

- LSA
 - not as good in detecting heterogeneity (three variant types detected)
 - the resulting semantic space generalizes towards the most salient aspects of the corpus
- LDA
 - can associate topics with different variant types
 - more even distribution across topics

LSA variant types and dimensions

DEATH OF A BRIDE BEFORE WEDDING
 d1: mother child young baby shepherd wreath blood
 d4: Ljubljana linden lover boy seduce chamber Tonček
 d5: Breda Ljubljana groom mother-in-law linden baby Turk
 d6: Breda accident evil house mother-in-law sister groom
 d8: Ljubljana brother linden sea shirt prefer wash lover

NUN'S SUICIDE FOR LOVE
 d2: convent Ursula nun baptism godmother ring blood
 d3: convent Ursula nun baptism godmother shepherd wreath

HUNTER SHOOTS HIS LOVER AND HIMSELF
 d7: newpriest grave bury church rifle hunter student
 d9: Ljubljana linden rifle grave hunter shaking leaves
 d10: rifle hunter shaking Tonček leaves face pale

LDA variant types and topics

DEATH AT A REUNION
 t1: heart boy Breda head sad hunter Danube

MURDER OUT OF JEALOUSY
 t2: love sword kneel sharp neighbor boyfriend blame

BRIDE INFANTICIDE
 t3: home shepherd Mary uncle birth shred rockcradle

UNFAITHFUL STUDENT/NEW PRIEST
 t4: undertaker love priest parish love promise letter

NUN'S SUICIDE FOR LOVE
 t5: love Urška convent boy Jesus farewell sword

REJECTED LOVER
 t6: seduce blood house Vida linden Ljubljanians death

WIDOWER ON BRIDE'S GRAVE
 t7: tender abandon blood bread jesus rockcradle married

ABANDONED ORPHANS
 t8: bury window chamber wound grow crying dead

PUNISHMENT FOR THE WICKED SONS AND DAUGHTERS-IN-LAW
 t9: gold sea mountain rooster fear crying darling son

MISTRESS' LOYALTY REPAID
 t10: boy fenced heart nosegay dead grieve loyal

Voronoi diagram represents topological projections of both methods

Experiment two

- Do LDA topics correspond to song families?
 - can we distinguish between love and fate conflicts vs. family fates and conflicts
 - difficulty: intertextuality, themes in both are similar
- Agglomerative **hierarchical clustering** to cluster variant types according to
 - similarity of their average topic distributions
- Result
 - the semantic space does include some notion of song families
 - enables us to place individual (also new or unknown) songs into this space and study their relations to existing materials.

family clusters 1 (2:6) and 4 (13:31)

- hunter earth unfortunately rifle **son mother** remember
- noble castle **son** stand cry dress letter dress give
- **mother wife children** find gold adultery measure colorful stick boy
- mountain will water **mother** hero angry dam girlfriend mother-in-law
- **brother father** house dear ours sister see
- tender live leave quickly name call barely crown world beg

love clusters 2 (17:11) and 3 (6:4)

- field three maid sun golden like ark sea **lover**
- things **husband** voice eat say young white know sin school
- **mistress** unlock boy saint window pot die lie
- stepmother run home getup graveyard rough get out go home

Experiment three

- Can LDA detect major themes characteristic for individual variant types
- Supervised learning: **Labeled LDA**
 - predefined labels for topical distributions
 - LLDA learns topic distributions for the labels
- Manually annotated selected variants with labels (18% of the corpus)
 - trained the model
- Inference on the entire corpus
 - yields distributions over labels for each song

Experiment three

- Most variants share multiple topics, with the main topic for each shown as most salient
 - e.g. Mother prevents her son’s marriage
- Disambiguation of similar topics (e.g. unhappy love)

Side project - TextExplore

- Enable non-programmers to experiment with topic models

The screenshot shows the TextExplore interface with the search term "ubiti, ljubiti". The main area displays a "TOPIC" visualization, which is a line graph showing the frequency of the topic over time from 1700 to 1950. The y-axis represents percentage from 0% to 100%. The graph shows a relatively low but fluctuating frequency, with a notable peak around 1800.

On the left side, there is a sidebar with navigation icons and a list of words associated with the topic. The words are: iti, žlahten, priti, stati, trije, govoriti, reči, grad, toko, hitro, dati, marjetica, hud, jest, storiti, prinesti, vzeti, ven, kri, dom.

Below the graph, there is a section titled "TOP DOCUMENTS IN" with a "clear selected year" button. The top document is "266. NEZVESTA GOSPA S TREMI STRAŽARJI - A / 5." by Ljudska pesem, dated 1839, from the Celja region. It includes two stanzas of text: "1. Gospa postavlja vahte tri, / kedaj bojo šli gospod damo." and "2. U prvi uri te noči [...]". The second document is "22. PRED ZMAJEM REŠENO DEKLE / 1." by Ljudska pesem, dated 1839, from the Kranjsko region.

Side project - TextExplore

- Enable non-programmers to experiment with topic models
 - import corpus
 - create topic models (Mallet)
 - visualize documents, topics, time, location

266. NEZVESTA GOSPA S TREMI STRAŽARJI - A / 5.

Ljudska pesem
1839, okolica Celja
SLP5: DRUŽINSKE PRIPOVEDNE PESMI

PREVIEW	LEMMATISED	TOPIC -	
topic	ljubica iti fant stati reči lipa odpreti micka priti ležati svoj ljub roka kam sinoči hitro vzeti dekcle ljuba mlad		%
topic	srce oče ljub videti mati svoj kri sin gora hoteti vzeti moči storiti kak priti hiša prositi sestra dati smrt		%
topic	svet duša iti anton pekel vrata trije bog menih ven nebo slišati vprašati hitro star priti peter nebesa jest močno		%
topic	iti govoriti sestrica študent jest toko mlad imeti vol dati priti glava trije zlat seja brat bel črn neja bratec		%
topic	trije priti mrtev hanžek iti ležati delati fantič hitro dati zvoniti nesti fant štirje bel bolan živ umreti grob vstati		%
topic	ime roka hoditi imeti drag živeti smeti znati priti črn mlad svoj grob puška gora lovec povedati dekcle vzeti soldat		%
topic	marija jezus svet božji iti nesti pot gora devica nebeški nebesa priti prositi marij pomagati trije ljub vprašati usmiljen jožef		%
topic	mlad dati iti bog ančka bel imeti vida hala sinek olga star kača hlapec stati prelep adam eva peljati gledati		%
topic	voda morje marija grešnik jezus greh stati teči človek gora vstati bister jen barka svet barčica plavati drevo goreti moči		%
topic	bog ležati priti poslati dati vzeti umreti janez bolan iti svet duša živeti deklica mašnik imeti moliti dekcle spovedati milo		%

Conclusion

- LDA can uncover typical characteristics of individual variant types
 - enables classification of unknown materials
 - discover relationships (similarities and differences) in the corpus
- Future work:
 - more song families
 - further develop visualization, exploration
 - relations between lyric and melodic spaces

